

CULTIVATING BIODIVERSITY: AN EXPERIMENTAL EDUCATIONAL PROJECT IN THE ECOLOGICAL FIELD

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Abstract

This project aimed to foster an ecological mindset in future citizens through the observation of Agrobiodiversity, involving two third-grade classes of “D. Manin” primary School belonging to “Tina Anselmi” Educational Complex (Dolo, Venice, Italy) during the school year 2023. The lack of scientific culture is one of the issues affecting our society. In this perspective, developing scientific competence through teaching techniques and methodologies that favour significant learning as active learning is essential. The research aims to compare the didactic efficacy of the experimental active method to the traditional transmissive method in lifelong learning prospecting. Furthermore, this research compares the appreciation and sharing with the surrounding community of the pupils about the information and educational experiences acquired during the activities in the two research groups. The two groups experienced two methods in studying genetic biodiversity: the experimental group achieved this concept by observing green seeds. The first observation involved seeds of different species, and the second was circumscribed to beans of different varieties provided by the INCREASE project. The control group approached the topic with a traditional method. The path was preceded by a questionnaire survey to identify the teaching methodologies and practices applied by the science teachers of the plexus. To verify the homogeneity and the pre-knowledge of the two research groups, an interview and the test ex-post were administered at the end of the experimental path (ex-post). This test was also issued after two months (follow-up) to compare the results of the two research groups, together with a self-assessment aimed at detecting the level of satisfaction and usefulness of the activities. A questionnaire created ad hoc was proposed to the parents of the pupils to understand the share and satisfaction demonstrated by the students in the family environment. Different levels of understanding of the topic emerged between the two research groups, with a higher percentage of correct answers from the experimental group in the ex-post and follow-up questionnaires. The answers provided by the experimental group to the open question concerning the examples of genetic varieties were much more varied and diversified than the examples provided by the control group students. The results of this research further confirm that the experimental method is more effective than the traditional method. No different levels of share of experiences and topics emerged, but the experimental group expressed a higher approval. This research further confirmed the experimental method's effectiveness and demonstrated that it increases the interest of pupils, the cornerstone in developing an ecological mindset and spreading scientific culture.

Keywords: biodiversity, INCREASE, laboratory didactics, science education, seeds.

1 INTRODUCTION

Science teaching is important by generating a scientific culture that allows students to become active and aware citizens (Longo, 1998; Santovito, 2015; Barbacovi et al., 2018; Bolzon et al., 2022). The absence of this culture, highlighted by the Eurobarometer (2021) data, is also related to the teaching methodologies applied in science teaching. In particular, the transmissive method is based on verbal teaching and firmly based on using school aid. It fuels the idea that science can describe the world entirely and induces "miraculous" expectations or distrust towards science in citizens (Rossi & Santovito, 2016; Capparotto et al., 2017; Perazzone, 2019; Cazzador et al., 2022). The transmissive method is based on a positivist vision of science by transmitting "certain notions". Furthermore, in this method, the teacher is expected to be the centre, while the student takes on a passive role. It reduces the students' motivation and interest. On the contrary, as Bruner and Vygotskij stated, the students are the protagonists of their learning. The challenge for teachers is stimulating interest and curiosity in the investigation (Alfieri et al., 2000; Toninato & Santovito, 2015; Chiesa et al., 2019; Corbolino et al., 2020). It is possible through the active-experimental method, thanks to which scientific competence is developed. It includes acquiring fundamental knowledge and a method to increase personal knowledge (Favaron et al., 2017; Perazzone, 2019; Tonon et al., 2020; De Rossi et al., 2022). One of the primary methodologies of the active method is the laboratory. It is a dialogic environment in which different cognitive styles are stimulated (Alfieri et al., 1995; Lago et al., 2017; Forlin et al., 2018; Perazzone, 2019). In the laboratory, pupils can develop problem-solving skills and implement their knowledge of the scientific method. It gives students a research methodology (Tonon et al., 2013; Santovito, 2015; Gaiotto & Santovito, 2016; Gaiotto et al., 2020).

Considering the few hours allocated to teaching this school subject, the active method allows us to deal with the "founding cores" and enables further in-depth analysis and knowledge (Todaro Angelillo, 2001; Gaiotto et al., 2013; Longo, 2014; Lui et al., 2019). There is also an ecological perspective that connects the microcosm of the individual with the macrocosm of the Earth: it is at this age that the child acquires "ecological thinking" and learns about respect for nature as a logical condition for better living with ourselves (Santovito, 2015; Trevisan & Santovito, 2015; Grando et al., 2018a; Grando et al., 2018b). Furthermore, through the teaching of ecology, "ecological identity" is developed and understood as a way of perceiving ourselves concerning the ecosystems on which we depend (Fassinato et al., 2018; Tura et al., 2018; Gallina et al., 2019; Perazzone, 2019). Education shall make students protagonists in a continuous search for balance between humanity and natural systems instead of their domination. It is why ecology and environmental education are two sides of the same coin (Amati & Modelli, 1993; Bertoncetto et al., 2023; Massignani et al., 2023; Toninato et al., 2023).

2 PURPOSE OF RESEARCH

The study aims to test the effectiveness and efficiency of an educational project conducted through experimental, observational and comparative methods. The active method was compared to traditional teaching. The traditional transmissive method is based on the oral transmission of the contents of the subject. On the other hand, the active-experimental method is a method of scientific investigation. It involves collecting measurable data through observations and experiments related to a specific phenomenon. With this information, it is possible to formulate various hypotheses.

The second objective of the research is to verify any differences in the degree of sharing of the topics addressed with the two teaching methods by the students with the small community around them (their families).

The experimental project is based on the theme of specific and genetic biodiversity. Therefore, the project is based on the objectives of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) adopted by the United Nations in 2015 to encourage quality education, including education for sustainable development. Tomorrow's environment depends on today's children (Santovito, 2015; Dal Pozzo et al., 2023; Massarin et al., 2023; Trevisan et al., 2023). The protection of biodiversity is a much-discussed topic nowadays, so raising pupils' awareness on this topic is essential. The talk of the "sixth mass extinction" deals with agri-food biodiversity

(Diamond, 1987; Kolbert, 2014; Zandonella Necca et al., 2014; Zanata et al., 2020). Agricultural systems have developed their biodiversity, which helps them maintain their stability and resilience. This biodiversity, however, is in decline due to intensive agriculture based on monoculture, which began with the Green Revolution of the mid-twentieth century. This revolution led to genetic selection, heavy mechanical processing, abundant mineral fertilisation and the compromise of aquifers. In this way, more food was obtained, but less nutrient-rich. In response to these changes that have led to the decline of agri-food biodiversity, the SDGs set targets for the reduction of habitat degradation, the conservation of biodiversity and the promotion of the sharing of genetic resources (Vitale, 2011). The latter is the objective of the INCREASE Project, which provided information and seeds of several genetic bean varieties for this study. This project deals with the decentralised conservation of agricultural genetic resources, specifically related to pulses. INCREASE conserves, analyses and collects data on SSD (Single Seed Descendent) also through the involvement of citizens at an international level. They analyse the seeds using transcriptomic and metabolic techniques (Bellucci et al., 2021; Cortinovic et al., 2021; Papa, 2022). INCREASE conserves and analyses legumes because they are fundamental plants for the agri-food sector. They have a high protein content, are low in fat, and are nitrogen-fixing plants. The nitrates they produce replace synthetic fertilisers, thus eliminating 3% of global CO₂ (Bellucci et al., 2021; Papa, 2022). Therefore, legumes benefit sustainable agriculture.

3 EXPERIMENTAL PHASE

3.1 Field of intervention

In this study, we used the experimental method to study specific and genetic biodiversity. Comparative-observational methods were used to macroscopically observe the shapes and colours of seeds of five types of vegetable families. Then, they were classified into different species by carefully observing and comparing the morphology and phenotypic characteristics of the plant types. The same observational-comparative investigation was carried out with the seeds of different genetic varieties of beans donated to us by the INCREASE Project. By comparing the seeds and shoots of plants of other species and plants of different genetic varieties of the same species, the children could detect the numerous differences at the phenotypic level between plants of different species and the less evident but existing differences between plants of different bean varieties.

The activity was carried out in two third-grade classes in a primary school in Dolo (Venice, Italy). One class was the experimental group, while the other was the observational control group, where the teacher continued to teach the students using the traditional oral approach. This choice arose from the desire to observe a comparison between the two teaching methods, evaluate the value and effectiveness of the experimental method in scientific education, and also from a lifelong learning perspective. The experimental group is made up of 17 pupils, while the control group is made up of 18 students. The two groups follow the same science program according to the curriculum.

3.2 Experimental plan

In the experimental group, the research project lasted 8 hours. In the control group, teaching lasted 5 hours, using the traditional oral approach. The entire experimental project was carried out according to the subdivisions shown in Table 1.

Table 1. *Experimental Plan*

EXPERIMENTAL GROUP	CONTROL GROUP
<i>Pre-test administration.</i>	Pre-test administration.
<i>Survey of prior knowledge on the definition of biodiversity.</i>	Definition of biodiversity.
<i>First experimentation of species biodiversity through the observational-comparative method.</i>	

<i>Definition of hypotheses through the data collected.</i>	
<i>Detection of changes in the growth of early shoots.</i>	Definition of species biodiversity.
<i>Re-definition of hypotheses through the data collected.</i>	
<i>Second experimentation of genetic biodiversity through the observational-comparative method.</i>	
<i>Detection of changes in the growth of early shoots.</i>	Definition of genetic biodiversity.
<i>Brainstorming starting from previous hypotheses. Analysis of data collected to refute or confirm hypotheses.</i>	
<i>Discussion on the advantages of agri-food biodiversity.</i>	
<i>Post-test administration and self-assessment.</i>	Post-test administration and self-assessment.
<i>Follow-up test administration (after two months).</i>	Follow-up test administration (after two months).
<i>Administration of questionnaires to families.</i>	Administration of questionnaires to families.

3.3 Methodologies

During the experiment, we used different active teaching methodologies. The main one was the laboratory methodology (Masiero et al., 2023; Rossi et al., 2023; Tonon et al., 2023). It consisted of collecting measurable data through observation and experimentation regarding a phenomenon and formulating hypotheses, which can be confirmed or rejected experimentally. Specifically, to apply the scientific method, observations were made with the naked eye and with scientific tools; hypotheses were formulated about the observations; the hypotheses were redefined based on the new observations; comparisons were made between different species and different genetic varieties; the initial assumption was confirmed or rejected.

The teaching methodologies of discussion through brainstorming in small groups or with the entire class were fundamental to applying the scientific method. One innovative element in this teaching type was the use of new technologies, which proved essential in the research project. These happened through the use of the interactive whiteboard and the use of Post-it notes to register ideas and compare them with their classmates.

4 RESULTS

This project initially took place with the observation of the seeds of different species and the classification through an observation grid, subsequently, the children observed seeds of different genetic varieties of bean.

Figure 1: First experimentation of species biodiversity through the observational-comparative method.

Figure 2: Genetic biodiversity of bean.

The students were invited to express the known biodiversity concepts in the first lesson. The clinical conversation was stimulated by observing two images, one depicting agriculture based on monoculture and the other depicting sustainable agriculture. The students thought about the word biodiversity by dividing it into "bio" (life) and "diversity". Afterwards, we asked the students to observe, separate and classify seeds using magnifying glasses, a precise scale, a ruler and an observation grid. In this way, they were introduced to observe and describe the phenotypic differences of different species of vegetable plants (Figure 1). During the week and in the following lessons, the students noted/noticed how much water was given to each seed and the changes in the sprouts. The same systematic observation was made for the different genetic varieties of beans. The students observed how the seeds of various species had many phenotypic differences.

In contrast, the seeds of different genetic varieties of beans initially seemed very different, but they also found many similarities (Figure 2). Thanks to these observations, it was possible to introduce the definition of species and genetic biodiversity. Thus, it was possible to think and discuss the advantages of genetic biodiversity in agriculture.

5 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The purposes of this study include testing the effectiveness of the experimental method compared to the traditional method of science teaching. In formal education, knowledge is passively transmitted from teacher to student. Students learn through deductive methods from teachers providing solutions and answers to problems. Teachers constantly refer to the textbook as the basis for all activities. Traditional methods emphasise teaching, and the child's learning is bound to the background (Pavan & Santovito, 2014; Santovito, 2015; Palmieri et al., 2019).

On the contrary, laboratory teaching favours inductive methods. It allows students to discover the laws, rules and constants of the problem under consideration, learn through discovery, build knowledge networks in social interactions with peers, and experience all observed and studied phenomena. The student becomes the protagonist of the learning process, and the teacher acts as an indirect professional guide (Santovito, 2015; Meneghetti et al., 2017; Masiero et al., 2022; Pasquetto et al., 2023). The comparison between the experimental-active method and the traditional-transmissive method was made based on the results obtained in the tests administered before (ex-ante test), after (ex-post test) and two months after the project (follow-up test). In this way, it was possible to verify learning from a life-long learning perspective, even in the long term. Another tool used was a process evaluation notebook to evaluate skills. Finally, a self-assessment test was administered to detect the satisfaction and usefulness of the proposed activities. A questionnaire was addressed to the student's parents to understand the sharing and level of satisfaction demonstrated by the students in the family environment.

Figure 3: Comparison of average success rates.

Quantitatively speaking, the results confirmed the initial hypothesis: different levels of understanding of the topic emerged between the two research groups, with a higher percentage of correct answers by the experimental group in the ex-post and follow-up questionnaire. As one can notice from the graph of Figure 3, the result of the ex-post test is that compared to the ex-ante test, the control group had an increase in the average percentage of correct answers by 36%. However, the experimental group had an increase in the average success rate of 45% from the data collected with the ex-ante test. If the results are analysed from a lifelong learning perspective, comparing the results of the ex-post test with the follow-up test, the control group decreased the average percentage of correct answers by 8%. In comparison, the experimental group resulted in a reduction of the average success rate of 5%. As highlighted by the literature, science teaching based on the transmission of oral information may appear positive in the short term but not from a lifelong learning perspective.

Furthermore, it is highlighted that through a qualitative analysis of the test answers, the experimental group students consistently reported very varied examples of genetic biodiversity, drawing from everyday life experiences and not just from what emerged in the classroom during the course designed by me. In the follow-up test, the experimental group students reported examples observed at the Botanical Garden of Padua and of the plants whose seeds the class teachers gave them as gifts. Conversely, the control group stuck to the examples presented in class during the course. In the follow-up test, ten students out of eighteen in the control group could not answer the only open-ended question asking them to write two examples of genetic biodiversity.

Finally, the second research hypothesis was only partially confirmed. No differences emerged in the degree of sharing of the student's experiences with their parents. However, the degree of satisfaction expressed by the families was 28% higher in the experimental group. The results of the self-assessment also confirm it. In particular, considering the answers provided by the students in the self-evaluation questionnaire, it was found that the class particularly appreciated the practical, engaging, active and laboratory activities in which knowledge was acquired through the scientific approach. Therefore, the experience of the experiment increased interest among the students, and as previously mentioned, it is a fundamental element for developing the "ecological mentality", that every child should develop (Longo, 2014; Santovito, 2015; Perazzone, 2019).

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